

The Technician Commitment: Transforming Technical Careers through Culture Change

Dr Simon W Breeden

Technician Commitment
UK Institute for Technical Skills & Strategy
University of Nottingham, UK

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@simonbreeden

Get your thinking caps on!

Dr Simon W Breeden

I very much like and encourage engagement and challenge
Please do ask questions (at the end)
Write in chat as we go along and I will get to them (or reply after)
Don't be shy!

www.linkedin.com/in/simonbreeden

@simonbreeden

UNITED KINGDOM

TRENT BRIDGE
EST. 1838

There is only one football team in Manchester, right?!

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World leading research and innovation solves global challenges

Collaborative teams drive success

Team Science needs diversity of talent, skills and insight

Technician ~~Commitment~~

-But professor, I don't understand how this lab produces so much high quality research when it's full of **bottle washers!**

**“I’m just the
technician”**

The Technical Community

“Research technicians and technology and skills specialists (collectively referred to as Research Technical Professionals or RTPs) have expert knowledge and technical competence in their field. These may include but are not limited to – data scientists, data engineers, archivists, informaticians, statisticians, software developers, audio-visual technologists, technical professional staff and individuals staffing and managing core research facilities across all disciplines”.

UKRI 2023

Further example job titles:

Research Technician, **Staff Scientist**, Technical Specialist, **Core Facility Manager**, Operator, **Research Infrastructure Staff**, Shared Resource Laboratory Staff, **Experimental Officer**, Technical Manager, **Technologist**, Research Associate

The Technical Community

- Technicians a vital part of teams yet experience a lack of visibility & recognition
- UK has an identified shortage of technical skills and roles
- Technical community has an ageing population & significant EDI challenges
- Technical career pathways are unclear/tricky to navigate
- Initiatives to ensure a pipeline of technical talent in HE & research are globally still few and far between – and coupled with a lack of visibility of technical careers makes it hard to attract/create pipeline
- Breadth and depth of roles considered technical – a complex landscape
- Lack of professional identity – negative connotations sometimes associated with the word ‘technician’

Firm footing

Technicians, the academy's 'Cinderellas', play vital roles and deserve proper recognition and support, argue Kelly Vere and Roger Murphy

have been prevented from participating in the opportunities on offer to their academic counterparts.

Despite their undoubted talents and growing importance to the UK academy, technicians often feel undervalued, under-represented within the decision-making structures of the university and excluded from the activities, events and facilities that would allow them to carry out their work on a par with other staff groups often performing similar roles. Many identify a glass ceiling that is hard to penetrate for those with a technical background.

There are also problems in relation to trade union activity. Many technical staff are members of the Universities Superannuation Scheme and the University and College Union negotiates on issues such as USS pension reforms, yet the UCU appears to exclude technicians from the list of university staff eligible to join it.

Efforts are being made to tackle many of these problems. As "Technically indispensable" showed, some positive schemes are emerging to recruit, train and accredit technicians. Valuable work is being undertaken by Higher Education and Technicians Education and Development, a small, recently formed organisation that works with subscribing institutions to try to address some of the issues that concern practitioners. In addition, the

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University of Nottingham > News > Press releases > 2015 > June

2015 Higher Education Technicians' Summit celebrating the talent of technicians

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30 Jun 2015 16:30:00.00 PA 98/15

The University of Nottingham intensive universities across the UK celebrating the achievements of technicians who underpin the Higher Education Technicians' Summit.

The Summit recognised the 'heroes' of UK higher education who support research and innovation in universities and the Science and Technology Facilities Council (STFC).

Click here for full story

Kelly Vere, Conference Chair, said: "We are celebrating the achievements of our technical staff. We are thrilled to have the support of a number of leading universities fully committed to the pursuit of excellence in education and beyond."

Celebrating the talent of technicians

Call for nominations Celebrating best practice in technical services

Do you know a technician whose work goes above and beyond? Nominate them for an inaugural **Papin Prize**.

For more info on categories and nomination visit www.nottingham.ac.uk/techsummit

Prizes will be awarded at the 2015 Higher Education Technicians' Summit, Jubilee Campus, Nottingham, on Tuesday 30 June.

Nottingham Post

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Crime Education Business Health Politics Blogs Letters

Award success for university staff

By Nottingham Post | Posted: September 03, 2014

Comments (0)

WORK aimed at raising the profile of more than 700 technical staff at the University of Nottingham has been recognised with an award.

The [Making a Difference](#) accolade was handed to the university's Technical Focus Group, which was formed in 2013 to ensure recognition of the institution's technicians.

The award was presented as part of the 5-Lab awards, during a gala dinner at King's College London.

Nottingham vice-chancellor Professor Sir David Greenaway said: "This award shows that the work we are doing to support our technical staff is of real importance. It is unimaginable that we could deliver what we do without a really well qualified and motivated technical staff."

theguardian

News Sport Comment Culture Business Money Life & style

Professional Higher education - HEA partner zone Learning at

Advertisement feature

Higher Education Network partner

HEA announces STEM Technicians of the Year 2014

HEA awards nine technicians for their work in supporting the student learning experience within STEM departments

Guardian Professional

Winners of HEA STEM Technicians of the Year 2014. Photograph: HEA

“We work in exciting environments, often at the cutting edge of research that makes a real difference to people’s lives. Technical skills are crucial to innovation and the wider economy. A career as a technician is stimulating, rewarding and definitely #notjustforboys!”

Kelly Vere, STEM Technician of the Year 2014

#notjustforboys

An Evolving Landscape

2017

2018

2020

2021

2022

2024

Technician Commitment

Established with 36 UK founding signatories.

Sector Reports

Technician Commitment: One Year In

2019

Sector Reports

Technicians: Providing frontline and vital support for student health and wellbeing

Equality, Diversity & Inclusion: A Technician Lens

Research England funds TALENT. £5m to advance status and opportunity for technical community in UK higher education & research

Sector Report COVID-19 The Impact on Technicians in UK Higher Education and Research

The government's UK Research and Development Roadmap launches, outlining the UK's vision and ambition for science, research, innovation. (References Technician Commitment)

UKRI publishes Technician Action Plan

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Equality, Diversity and Inclusion: UK Technicians' Experiences During the Covid-19 Pandemic

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The Role of Technicians in Knowledge Exchange An explorative study

Technician Commitment: Progress and Impact

Government launches R&D People and Culture Strategy. A vision and call to action to ensure people are recognised as being at the core of R&D.

Sector Reports

The TALENT Commission

Research Culture: A Technician Lens

2023

Publish sector report:

Economic Benefits of implementing TALENT Commission Recommendations

Awarded Research England funding to establish ITSS - £5.5m.

Launched August 2023

Convened stakeholder engagement with URKI for REF 2029 PCE consultation

National opportunities launched:

- Leadership programmes
- Knowledge Exchange Placement Scheme
- Funding Call for Physics Technical Apprentices

New National Technical Networks

£16m EPSRC Strategic Technical Platforms

Technician Commitment

Over 120 signatories and supporters – including international members

Increased sector awareness and engagement with the need to consider technical skills and roles strategically and drive culture change

Technician Commitment

PROUD SUPPORTER OF THE
Technician Commitment

#TechsCommit

VISIBILITY

Ensuring technicians are **visible** within and beyond higher education and research institutions

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RECOGNITION

Supporting technicians to gain **recognition** through registration

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DEVELOPMENT

Enabling career **progression** for technicians through clear pathways

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SUSTAINABILITY

Safeguarding technical skills across the organisation by **using** and **developing** expertise

University of
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Technician Commitment

#TechsCommit

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Technician Commitment

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VISIBILITY

Ensuring technicians are **visible** beyond higher education and research institutions

The Technician Commitment Signatory Form

The Science Council is working with partners to ensure greater visibility and recognition for technicians in higher education. The Technician Commitment has been developed to address the key issues affecting the technical community in academia and research. In becoming a signatory to the Science Council's Technician Commitment, University of York hereby commits to take action across five key areas:

Visibility

Ensure that all technicians within the organisation are identifiable and that the contribution of technicians is visible within and beyond the institution

Recognition

Support technicians to gain recognition through professional registration

Career Development

Enable career progression opportunities for technicians through the provision of clear, documented career pathways

Sustainability

Ensure the future sustainability of technical skills across the organisation and that technical expertise is fully utilised

Evaluating Impact

Regularly assess the impact of actions taken in support of the commitment to ensure their effectiveness

Signed: *Brian Fulton*

[name; position] Brian Fulton, Dean of the Faculty of Sciences
[institution name] University of York
[date] 7 April 2017

Nominated Institutional Lead

We hereby nominate Brian Fulton, Dean of the Faculty of Sciences as the lead contact for taking forward our commitment:

Email: brian.fulton@york.ac.uk
Phone: 01904 32 4241

Ensuring technicians to gain **recognition** through professional registration

Ensuring technicians to gain **recognition** through professional registration

PROUD SUPPORTER OF THE
Technician Commitment

DEVELOPMENT

Enabling career **progression** for technicians through clear pathways

Ensuring technicians to gain **recognition** through professional registration

Ensuring technicians to gain **recognition** through professional registration

University of Nottingham
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Technician **Commitment**

UK universities sign up to 'technician commitment'

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The Crick @TheCrick · Sep 28

We've backed a pledge to support science technicians to ensure greater visibility, recognition & career development. crick.ac.uk/news/news-arch...

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Russell Group @RussellGro

Technical staff are vital to de...
teaching #TechsCommit #NS

Make it

BREAKING: Half of UK universities back pledge to support their technical staff technicians.org.uk/news/half-uk-u...
#TechsCommit #NSLive

De Montfort Uni DMU @dmuleicester · Apr 12

DMU affirms commitment to its technicians by signing sector-wide @TechsCommit pledge dmu.ac.uk/about-dmu/news... #loveDMU #IchoseDMU #TechsCommit

3 7

Keele University @KeeleUniversity · Apr 12

We're proud to support the **Technician Commitment** — a pledge to safeguard and improve vital technical skills in higher education bit.ly/2HuCWF3
#TechsCommit

4 8

"Technicians probably haven't

the

nstitute @sangerinstitute · Apr 12

joined the Technician Commitment - pledging action to support and our #technicians. #TechsCommit

Technician Commitment @TechsCommit

Vice-chancellors and industry leaders back pledge to support technical staff technicians.org.uk/news/vice-chan...
#TechsCommit

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Technician Commitment

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Technician Commitment action plan 2024-2027

The Crick is a signatory to the Technician Commitment, a sector-wide initiative led by the Science Council and the Gatsby Foundation aiming to address the particular career challenges faced by technical and scientific staff.

ment initiative

Support from sector institutions

Support from sector institutions

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Royal Society and the Technician Commitment

← Reports and publications

03 February 2021

The Royal Society is a formal supporter of the Technician Commitment initiative.

The Technician Commitment aims to ensure visibility, recognition, career development and sustainability for technicians working in higher education and research, across all disciplines. We are a strong advocate of these values. Here are some of the ways we are meeting them:

Visibility

We have been actively raising the profile and awareness of technical roles through our policy work including representations to the UK government and Parliament and by having a technical representative on our Research System Community of Interest.

Recognition

Technicians can be listed as authors or contributors in publications in all our journals. They can also act as co-reviewers.

Marking the Society's 350th anniversary in 2010, we recognised and rewarded excellence in supporting science, technology, engineering and mathematics in the UK with the Hausdöbe Award. Four technicians were among the winners.

The Royal Society's journal of the history of science, *Notes and Records*, contains a [special issue on Technicians](#). It includes articles on the invisible technicians in the industrial revolution and technicians in mid-twentieth-century British medical research.

Career development

Technicians can be nominated or apply for a number of Royal Society awards such as the Athena Prize which recognises teams who have contributed to the advancement of diversity in science, technology, engineering and mathematics (STEM) and the David Attenborough Award which rewards individuals for outstanding public engagement with science. [Find out more about our awards here.](#)

Sustainability

We continue to advocate for technical roles in our policy work such as in our work with the other National Academies on the [future immigration system](#).

Professor Dame Athene Donald FRS, Chair of the Society's Research System Community of Interest, is represented on the [Midlands Innovation TALENT Policy Commission](#), a project which aims to lead and influence change to advance status and opportunity for technical skills, roles and careers in UK Higher Education.

Supporting technicians in chemistry

Technicians are vital to the advancement of the chemical sciences and the health of our economy. We intend to influence the development of technical education for the chemical sciences, working with educators, policy makers and employers to ensure a supply of skilled technicians entering and staying in the sector.

The Science Council's Technician Commitment initiative ensures that universities and research institutions place technicians at the forefront of what they're doing.

As an official supporter, the Royal Society of Chemistry is pleased to outline our action plan which follows the Technician Commitment's four pillars of Visibility, Recognition, Career Development and Sustainability.

Visibility Awards

To ensure a wide audience recognise the value of technicians, we offer a range of awards available to teams and individuals including the Higher Education Technical Excellence award, Industry Technician of the Year, and Apprentice of the Year.

Networking

Our networks provide opportunities for members to connect with each other face to face and online, with networks based on either regional area or specific subjects. With some funding available for travel, we bring people together to socialise, share ideas and collaborate.

Recognition Professional registration

The Registered Scientist (RSC) and Registered Science Technician (RSC(Tech)) awards recognise technicians' skills, knowledge and professionalism. These registers provide independent recognition of achieving and maintaining the exacting standards required to join the global community of professional scientists.

Accreditation

As well as providing a clear bespoke route to registered or chartered status for employees, our peer-reviewed accreditation provides employers with the confidence that their training and progression routes are of a recognised high standard. Accreditation helps companies to recruit and retain talented employees who are keen to develop their careers.

Career development Technician skills development grant

Our skills development grant allows technicians to undertake short to mid-term visits to organisations either overseas or within their country of residence. These trips will allow technicians to develop the skills and knowledge they need to elevate their career to the next level.

Discounted training courses

We will help technicians identify high quality training to support their career development goals with our database of peer-reviewed and approved courses. We are working in partnership with HEATED, the UK's leading provider of professional development and networking opportunities for the technical workforce, to offer our members discounts on their approved training courses.

Sustainability Outreach fund

Our outreach fund provides financial support to members, individuals and organisations to run chemistry-based public and schools engagement activities that inspire the next generation to choose chemistry and view a career as a technician in a new light.

Mentoring

We can offer mentors or mentoring opportunities to members of the RSC. The aim is to provide professional advice and greater clarity around career goals and networking that will help individuals to understand the opportunities that a career as a technician might offer.

Want help with implementing your action plan? Contact us on technicians@rsc.org.

Increased sector recognition

THE AWARDS

Outstanding Technician of the Year

2022 – Hong Ling
University of Reading

2021 – Andrew Filby
Newcastle University

2023 – Jason Daff
University of York

2024 – Jodie Chatfield
University of Nottingham

2025 – Jiteen Ahmed
Aston University

2020 – John Waters
University of Liverpool

2019 - Barbara Kunz
Open University

New research and policy insights into technical roles, skills and careers

New clearly defined career pathways for technical roles

Figure 11: Possible entry routes into technical careers within UK HE and research.
Source: interviews with technical managers and career specialists from a range of UK institutions and discipline areas.

UK government policy influence

GOV.UK Search

Coronavirus (COVID-19) | Guidance and support

Home > [Business and industry](#) > [Science and innovation](#) > [Research and development](#) > [UK Research and Development Roadmap](#)

Department for Business, Energy & Industrial Strategy

Policy paper

UK Research and Development Roadmap

Published 1 July 2020

Contents

- Foreword
- Executive Summary
- Being honest about where we need to improve
- Raising our research ambitions
- Inspiring and enabling talented people and teams
- Driving up innovation and productivity
- Levelling up R&D across the UK
- Being at the forefront of global collaboration
- Developing world-leading infrastructure and institutions
- Ensuring a healthy R&D system
- Next steps

Foreword

The UK is internationally recognised for our leadership in research, the excellence of our scientific institutions, and the innovation in our economy. We can proudly claim to be the nation that gave the world the steam engine and the jet engine. We discovered graphene and we decoded the structure of DNA. Today, we are by far the top destination in Europe for venture capital, with inward investors attracted by our talented and diverse workforce as well as our cutting-edge technologies and services.

The COVID-19 pandemic has shown all of us the vital importance of science and innovation. British researchers are at the forefront of global efforts to find a vaccine and are working hard to map out the impact of the pandemic on our lives and livelihoods. Organisations of all shapes and sizes have worked tirelessly to respond to the crisis in innovative new ways.

In March, the Chancellor announced a record increase in public investment in research and development (R&D) – committing to reaching £22 billion per year by 2024 to 2025. Just a few months on, this commitment has added importance. We will need to be even more creative and innovative to adapt to the 'new normal', and to recover swiftly from COVID-19. It is our duty to build a future which is greener, safer and healthier than before.

Launch of the future research assessment programme

Related content
Research En

19 May 2021

The four UK higher education funding bodies are launching the Future Research Assessment Programme.

 Department for
Business, Energy
& Industrial Strategy

R&D People and Diversity Strategy

People at the heart of R&D

 REF 2029
Research Excellence Framework

[REF](#) | [2029](#) | [2021](#) | [2014](#) | [RAE 2008](#)

[News](#) | [Publications](#) | [Guidance](#) | [Panels](#) | [Resources](#) | [About](#) | [Contact](#)

Recognising all those who drive research excellence: REF 2029 and research enabling staff

Kelly Vere,
Deputy Co-Chair
REF 2029 People and Diversity Advisory Panel

6 August 2025

REF 2029 will consider the collective endeavour of the institution and the many communities – academic, professional services and technical alike – who make research possible, and ensure research excellence.

One of the most exciting developments in the evolution of REF 2029 is the clear intention to recognise the contributions of **everyone** who enables or leads research. Initiatives like the **Technician Commitment** and the **Hidden REF** have worked hard to raise the visibility of research-enabling staff in universities, so it's fantastic to see this reflected in how we plan to assess research excellence in future.

Public outreach and engagement

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OBJECTS AND STORIES

LEARNING

MENU ▾ 🔍

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HOME → SEE AND DO

TECHNICIANS: THE DAVID SAINSBURY GALLERY

OPENS AUTUMN 2022

Step into the fascinating world of Technicians and take a peek behind the scenes in our brand new interactive gallery.

Experience what it's like to create visual effects on a blockbuster film set, analyse blood samples in a medical laboratory, operate a robot in a manufacturers workshop, fix a fault atop a wind turbine and much more.

FREE INTERACTIVE GALLERY

DATE: Opening autumn 2022

LOCATION: level 1

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International sharing of best practice

THE UNIVERSITY OF SYDNEY

Technician **Commitment**

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News_

University of Sydney joins Technician Commitment program

16 February 2023

Sydney becomes the first international signatory to UK-based initiative

Share

Technician Commitment

An Evolving Landscape

2017

Technician Commitment

Establish the Technician Commitment. It launches with 36 founding signatory institutions.

2018

Publish sector report:

Technician Commitment: One Year In

2019

Publish sector reports:

Technicians: Providing frontline and vital support for student health and wellbeing.

Equality, Diversity & Inclusion: A Technician Lens.

2020

Awarded Research England funding for TALENT – a £5M programme to advance status and opportunity for the technical community in UK higher education and research

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The government's UK Research and Development Roadmap launches, setting out the UK's vision and ambition for science, research and innovation (references Technician Commitment).

2021

Publish sector reports:

Equality, Diversity and Inclusion: UK Technicians' Experiences During the Covid-19 Pandemic.

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2022

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The TALENT Commission

Research Culture: A Technician Lens

Technician Commitment

Stands at over 110 signatory and supporter organisations

Increased sector awareness and engagement with the need to consider technical skills and roles strategically and drive culture change

Research
England

Programme Workstreams

A diagram consisting of three interconnected loops, resembling a chain or a series of overlapping circles, rendered in a glowing white outline. Each loop contains text and is positioned above a corresponding descriptive text block.

Policy
commission

Strategic insight into technical
skills of the future

Culture
change
projects

Driving culture change for the
technical community

Training and
empowerment

Career development for
technicians through tailored
technical training

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Transport, Manufacturing,
Cranfield University

Jhoen Ahmed
Head of Technical Services,
Aston University

Ray Chung
Head of University IT Support,
Loughborough University

Who are they?

Technicians & technical Staff

Academic staff

VCs & PVCs

Directors, CEOs, & sector leaders

Representatives from...

Higher Education Providers

Research Institutes

Funding Bodies

Learned Societies & Academies

Industry

Charitable Foundations

STEM, Creative Arts, IT, etc

Key Themes Explored

The TALENT Commission report

- A landmark policy report
- Research findings & evidence based recommendations
- Launched virtually in Feb 2022
- Parliamentary reception at the House of Lords in May 2022

Reception so far

← Back to Knowledge Hub

Governance News Alert

UKRI/Research England TALENT Commission report: Technical skills, roles and careers in UK higher education and research

Published: 03 February 2022

The TALENT Commission was launched in July 2020 to look at technical skills, roles and careers across UK higher education and research and is part of wider work by Research England to advance the status and opportunities of the technical community. The report is the result of 20 months of research and stakeholder engagement, including the largest survey of UK technical staff working in higher education and research ever undertaken, a range of focus groups and additional commissioned research projects on topics including funding and future technologies. The report outlines a set of principles and 16 recommendations, with further specifics to target stakeholder groups.

The full report can be found [here](#).

At a glance

The TALENT Commission Report

<https://www.researchprofessionalnews.com/rr-news-uk-research-councils-2022-2-role-of-technicians-in-teaching-and-research-underplayed/>

*ResearchProfessional News

UK Europe USA Australia & NZ Africa World Opinion Funding Insight Covid-19 Funding Opportunities

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WHAT DO TALENT COMMISSION REPORT FINDINGS MEAN FOR THE FUTURE OF TECHNICIANS? – A GW4 RESPONSE /

February 22, 2022

Sabrina Fairchild

Dr Sabrina Fairchild, GW4 Alliance Talent and Skills Manager, welcomes the TALENT Commission report, which has gathered new strategic insights into the UK's technical workforce in higher education and research.

PROFESSIONAL CAMPUS JOBS EVENTS RANKINGS STUDENT SC < Go back

Don't exclude technicians from decision-making, universities told

'Unsung heroes' of UK research are too often denied seat at the table, says major review of technical staff and skills

February 1, 2022

Jack Grove

Twitter: [@jgro_the](#)

FUNDERS 01 FEB 2022 |

Role of technicians in teaching and research 'underplayed'

By Chris Parr

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Talent Commission calls for better career opportunities for technical staff

Transforming the UK's Technical Talent: An opportunity for the HE and research sectors

10 March 2022

By Debra Humphris

Debra Humphris is Vice-Chancellor of the University of Brighton and was one of the Commissioners on the UKRI-Research England funded TALENT Commission, a national policy commission delivering strategic insight into the future of the UK's technical talent.

Collaboration isn't always easy in a competitive sector. But in the current higher education and research landscape, more strategic thinking by institutions, funders and policymakers

The TALENT Commission

Technical skills, roles and careers in
UK higher education and research

R9: Employers of technical staff should ensure visibility of clearly defined career pathways and progression routes, with accurate and standardised job descriptions for technical roles. Pilot activity should be considered by employers of technicians to explore new opportunities for progression routes akin to those available for academic roles.

Research Technical Professional Pathway

Figure 11: Possible entry routes into technical careers within UK HE and research.
Source: interviews with technical managers and career specialists from a range of UK institutions and discipline areas.

The TALENT Commission

Technical skills, roles and careers in UK higher education and research

R1: Employers of technical staff, funders, and government departments should employ a strategic approach to ensure the sustainability and appropriateness of technical skills and careers, at both a local and national level. This includes succession planning in individual organisations, investment in a new pipeline of technical talent and horizon scanning new and emerging technologies and skills. **Institutions should appoint a strategic lead for technical staff and skills in the organisation to lead this agenda, in collaboration with technical managers.**

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Manchester Metropolitan University

Recommendation 16:

“The TALENT Commission advises the creation of a new collaborative entity, provisionally to be called the UK Institute for Technical Skills & Strategy [working title] that builds on the multi-stakeholder approach of the Technician Commitment, to represent and provide a conduit to the technical community, advising government, sector initiatives, funding bodies and other organisations. We advise that the new entity works closely with the professional bodies and membership organisations to which technical staff belong to ensure connectivity, voice and visibility for the technical community.”

An Evolving Landscape

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Publish sector report:

Economic Benefits of implementing TALENT Commission Recommendations

Awarded Research England funding to establish ITSS - £5.5m.

Launched August 2023

Convened stakeholder engagement with URKI for REF 2029 PCE consultation

2024

National opportunities launched:

- Leadership programmes
- Knowledge Exchange Placement Scheme
- Funding Call for Physical Technical Apprentices

New National Technical Networks

£16m EPSRC Strategic Technical Platforms

Technician Commitment

Over 120 signatories and supporters – including international members

Increased sector awareness and engagement with the need to consider technical skills and roles strategically and drive culture change

UK Research and Innovation @UKRI_News · 6h

Technicians are essential to research & innovation. Through @ResEngland, we're pleased to support the new UK Institute of Technical Skills and Strategy @UniofNottingham.

More: mitalent.ac.uk/UK-ITSS #UKITSS

"The Institute of Technical Skills and Strategy will build on the great work of our technical community and Technician Commitment leads across the UK by providing advocacy and strategic leadership for the diverse technical community.

"Technicians, technologists, specialists and related roles across the Research & Innovation sector are vital to our strategy to create a diverse and inclusive system, supporting and enabling individuals, and the UK, to reach their full potential."

- Melanie Welham, UKRI Executive Champion for People, Culture & Talent.

Research England @ResEngland · 11h

Technicians are vital to the UK **research** & innovation system. We're pleased to be contributing to enhancing skills and developing careers through our support of the new national Institute of Technical Skills and Strategy @UniofNottingham - mitalent.ac.uk/UK-ITSS #UKITSS

"I'm pleased that Research England funding is supporting the new UK Institute of Technical Skills and Strategy.

"The Institute will enhance the skills base for technicians, help to raise the visibility of their vital contribution to UK research & innovation, and support their career development, and tackle a shortage of technicians.

"I look forward to seeing the impact the ITSS will have for technicians – from museum archivists right through to space technologists."

- Professor Dame Jessica Corner, Executive Chair of Research England

**Research
England**

**£5.5 million Investment to establish new
UK Institute for Technical Skills & Strategy**

UK INSTITUTE FOR
TECHNICAL
SKILLS & STRATEGY

Study A

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Sir Colin Cam

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Meet the team

Image: Flickr / Simon Walker

National Institute of Technical Skills and Strategy to support UK research and innovation launched

By **Reece Goodall**

Mar. 23, 2023

Posted in News

The UK is set to welcome a new £5.5 million national institute, with the aim of augmenting the country's technical capability and capacity across academia, research, education, and innovation. The initiative seeks to enable the UK to become a global powerhouse in science, engineering, and creative industries.

Our Vision

Powered by its technical workforce, the UK is a global leader in science, technology, engineering, medicine and the creative industries.

Technical careers are recognised, developed, respected and aspired to.

A Collaborative Initiative

Our Partners

**Research
& Policy
Group**

**Community
& Practice
Hub**

**Technician
Commitment**

**Learning &
Development
Academy**

**Education
& Pathways
Lab**

CONSULTING

**ITSS
International**

A man with short brown hair and glasses, wearing a red jacket over a blue shirt, is looking down at a green plant in a greenhouse. The background shows large windows and other plants. The image has a blue gradient overlay on the left side.

Technician Commitment

Leading a cultural shift at over 130 organisations that advocates for the technical profession and fosters positive working environments.

Research & Policy Group

Providing evidence-based insights and data and influencing policy to guide technical workforce development and investment.

New research and policy insights into technical roles, skills and careers

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Research Article

Technicians as teachers: the emerging role of technical staff within higher education teaching and learning environments

F. P. H. Wragg

Pages 1196-1210 | Received 05 Jul 2022, Accepted 14 Jun 2023, Published online: 10 Jul 2023

Cite this article | <https://doi.org/10.1080/0309877X.2023.2231380> | Check for updates

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In this article

- ABSTRACT
- Introduction
- Method
- Results

ABSTRACT

Technicians and technical staff are making increasingly significant contributions to the teaching and learning of undergraduate and postgraduate students in the UK. This paper reports on a survey of 1766 technical staff regarding their roles within teaching and learning environments, and a series of follow-up focus groups with 44 technical staff further exploring the roles, visibility, and

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Abstract

Knowledge exchange (KE) is becoming a strategic imperative for universities globally. Research examining KE has tended to focus on a limited and select group of stakeholders. This paper builds on calls for a wider consideration of KE activities and other contributors to the KE agenda. The technical community is one such group that has received little attention or acknowledgement of their part in KE. We argue that the technical community

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London Review of Education

LONDON
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EDUCATION

 UCLPRESS

Special issue: *Third space roles and identities in educational settings*

Research article

Crossing and dismantling boundaries: recognising the value of professional staff within higher education

Kelly Vere,¹

¹ UK Institute for Technical Skills and Strategy, University of Nottingham, Nottingham, UK

² Education and Student Success, University of Bristol, Bristol, UK

³ School of Cultures, Languages and Area Studies, University of Nottingham, Nottingham, UK

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How to cite

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Peer review

This article has been peer-reviewed through the journal's standard double-anonymous peer-review process, where both the reviewers and authors are anonymised during review.

[HOME](#) / [ARCHIVES](#) / NO. 33 (2025): SPECIAL EDITION, THIRD SPACE IN HE / Leadership, influence and credibility

Why is it problematic for technicians to say they teach in higher education?

Tim Savage

University for the Creative Arts

Kelly Vere

University of Nottingham

 <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2208-671X>

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.47408/jldhe.vi33.1191>

Keywords: technicians, technical, teaching, pedagogy, third space

ABSTRACT

This article challenges the popular misconception that technicians do not teach within higher education (HE). Writing from their experiences as technicians and educational researchers within the creative arts (Savage)

 PDF

PUBLISHED

30-01-2025

HOW TO CITE

Savage, T. and Vere, K. (2025) "Why is it problematic for technicians to say they teach in higher education?", *Journal of Learning Development in Higher Education* [Preprint], (33). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.47408/jldhe.vi33.1191>.

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Technical professionals can offer more than support

Too often seen as backroom staff, technical professionals are in fact key players in rethinking how universities operate. Kelly Vere explains how their insight and expertise are more vital than ever

COMMENT | 23/07/25

“At a recent Technician Commitment event held at Queen’s University Belfast, representatives from institutions across the UK shared practical and strategic actions they believe could help universities weather the current financial crisis”.

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Technicians in Higher Education and Research An Insight into Technical Careers, Roles and Contributions

Edited By [Kelly Vere](#)

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Oct 11, 2024 | Latest, Policy Consultations

Our response to The House of Lords Science and Technology Committee inquiry into engineering biology

Jul 2, 2024 | Policy Consultations

Our response to the Department for Education consultation on the Advanced British Standard

May 7, 2024 | Policy Consultations

Working with UK funding councils

Research Technical Professional and career progression - Mythbusting

UK Research
and Innovation

- RTPs cannot apply for funding – **yes they can!**
 - **Not true** – *UKRI will happily accept them as a PI or Co-I on an application, particularly for equipment funding (i.e. Strategic Equipment and Core Equipment) provided they meet the broader eligibility criteria.*
- RTPs have to be included as technicians on grants – **no they don't!**
 - **Not true** – *although RTPs could be included under technical costs, they do not have to be. They could be PI, Co-I, a Researcher Co-I or a named researcher.*
- Peer review is not something for RTP roles – **it absolutely is!**
 - **Not true** – *UKRI seek reviewers and panel members from the RTP community because they value the understanding and perspective they bring.*

New funding to support research technical professionals

Related content

- ⇒ [£1 billion doctoral training investment announced](#)
- ⇒ [£100 million investment in The Alan Turing Institute announced](#)

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£16 million support will focus on community-driven projects providing training and development for research technical professionals (RTP).

Community groups working to support technical and research software roles are set to benefit from a share of a new £16 million investment. The investment is by the Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council (EPSRC) and UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) Digital Research Infrastructure (DRI).

RTPs are vital to the effective operation of research infrastructure across the UK. They use their skills and experience to support academic and industrial research, as well as train users in the latest techniques and methods. As well as providing valuable additional skills to improve their long-term career prospects the 11 projects will train RTPs in areas such as:

- software development
- data management and processing
- materials science
- biomolecular engineering

The screenshot shows the REF 2029 website homepage. At the top, there is a navigation bar with tabs for REF, 2029, 2021, 2014, and RAE 2008. Below this is a header section with the REF 2029 logo and the text 'Research Excellence Framework'. To the right of the logo is a navigation menu with links for Home, News, Publications, Guidance, Panels, About, and Contact, followed by a search bar. The main content area features a large purple banner with the text 'Research Excellence Framework' and 'Securing a world-class, dynamic and responsive research base across the full academic spectrum within UK higher education'. Below this text are three buttons: 'Get involved', 'People, Culture and Environment (PCE)', and 'Timetable'.

The **REF** is the UK's system for assessing the quality of research in UK higher education institutions. It first took place in [2014](#) and [2021](#). The next exercise is planned for 2029.

Working with UK Academies

The screenshot shows the website for The Royal Society. At the top left is the Royal Society logo. A navigation menu includes links for Fellows, Events, Journals, Current topics, Grants, Medals and prizes, About us, and News and resources. A search icon and 'Sign in' link are on the right. The main content area features a breadcrumb trail 'Home / Events' and a large title: 'Recognising and developing technical talent: Strategies for growth and development'. Below the title, event details are listed: '21 May 2025', '09:00 - 17:00', 'The Royal Society', and 'Free'. An 'Add to calendar' button is positioned to the right of these details. The bottom half of the page is dominated by a photograph of the Royal Society's building, a grand neoclassical structure with a portico supported by four large columns. The number '7' is visible on the columns. A black metal fence runs along the base of the building.

Learning & Development Academy

Empowering future technical leaders, educators and practitioners through tailored learning and development programmes.

Learning and Development Academy

Technical development and leadership

A range of flagship national leadership and development programmes, designed for the technical community in academia (teaching and research roles) and research institutes.

- **Executive Programme in Strategic Technical Leadership**
- **Herschel Programme for Women in Technical Leadership**
- **Postgraduate Certificate in Higher Education Global for technical professionals**
- **Vivien Thomas Technical Leadership Programme**

SpringFest and WinterFest Online Learning Festivals

Bitesize learning and development opportunities delivered through a programme of online workshops. Topics include career planning, professional registration, panel discussions and more. Delivered by learning and development experts and volunteers from the technical community.

[View full programme and register for workshops.](#)

Project Management for Technicians

Learn new project management skills and tools to enhance your workload planning. Designed for technical professionals who have one, or more, packages of work to manage and deliver.

Technical Teaching Recognition Programme

Helping technical professionals who support learning to gain professional recognition. Designed for technical professionals who would like support applying for professional recognition via Advance HE.

Technician Career Development Programme

Understand your own strengths, skills, values and motivations to take the next step in your career through unique group coaching sessions.

Nottingham University Business School

Who we are

Executive Education

Custom programmes

[The Executive Programme
in Strategic Technical
Leadership](#)

Help to Grow:
Management

Masterclasses

Global opportunities

Meet the team

Contact the team

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Research

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People

The Executive Programme in Strategic Technical Leadership

This programme offers current strategic technical leaders the opportunity to develop key skills for the critical roles they hold in their organisations.

Participants will learn from guest speakers from across the UK higher education and research sector. Through cohort-based learning, individual reflection, and peer networking, participants will be equipped with skills to develop themselves as effective and influential strategic technical leaders.

Through this programme you will:

- gain a wider understanding of the UK higher education and research sector, its current affairs and the evolving landscape for technical staff
- establish your 'personal brand' and professional identity to grow your networks
- develop skills to influence key stakeholders and

HERSCHEL

Programme

For Women in Technical Leadership

Advancing Technical Careers and Building Communities

Over 400 workshops
delivered and nearly
6000 places taken up
by UK technicians

Community & Practice Hub

Cultivating a thriving, interconnected technical community, facilitating knowledge sharing and collaboration

ITSS Capabilities Sharing Showcase

Putting technical expertise at the forefront of the UK equipment sharing agenda

[SUBMIT NEW FACILITY OR UPDATE FACILITY DETAILS](#)

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Configuration: Acquity H-Class UPLC system coupled to triple quadrupole mass spectrometer. Ionisation: ESI, API ...

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Waters Synapt G2-Si

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We offer targeted quantitative assays for oxylipins, phospholipids (native and oxidised), cholesterol esters and sphingomyelins using LC/MS. We can fully ...

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Central Biotechnology Services- Cell analysis and imaging

ISO 9001 certified and GCLP accredited Flow cytometry and cell sorting facility. Multiple benchtop flow cytometry instruments including: a BD ...

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Equipment Sharing Fund

Accelerate your research, realise your research ambitions

[Home](#) » [What We Do](#) » [Equipment Sharing and Technology Expertise](#) » [Equipment Sharing Fund](#)

What is the fund?

The Equipment Sharing Fund allows researchers, PhD students and Research Technical Professionals (RTPs) to access cutting-edge research equipment, not available in their home institution.

People who access the equipment, will benefit from the expertise and knowledge of the technical experts who are central to managing the equipment and training others.

How does it work?

Funds cover the cost of initial analysis, helping to strengthen collaboration opportunities and ensure value for money within the UK's research and innovation ecosystem.

The fund opens for four rounds and will provide the full economic cost (fEC) or TRAC rate directly to the facility. [Find out when the fund opens and more about the criteria.](#)

[APPLY HERE](#)

ITSS TECHNOLOGY CAPABILITIES SHOWCASE

“The programme has been invaluable in providing access to equipment we would ordinarily not be able to access, and in generating preliminary data to support onward grant applications.”

Daniel Tonge, Keele University, used University of Nottingham's Next Generation Sequencing Facility

Benefits for researchers, PhD students

- Increase your understanding of technology and research practices
- Generate preliminary data for grant applications
- Unlock new research opportunities
- Network with technical professionals in your discipline
- Collaboration strengthens the research and innovation ecosystem, ensuring value for money

Knowledge Exchange Placement Programme

[Home](#) » Knowledge Exchange Placements

UK technical staff who want to expand their skills and knowledge in a specialist area through a placement, can now apply to the Technical Skills Knowledge Exchange Placement Programme.

Learn new specialist skills from leading experts, share and consolidate best practice across institutes, and network with fellow technicians.

[APPLY HERE FOR A
PLACEMENT](#)

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“The placement has been a rewarding learning experience, one that has contributed to

Morgan Shaw

University of Dundee to the University of Alberta

“Collaborating in person is essential to fully understand complex techniques and learn the small details that make a huge impact in reproducibility and standardisation.

Funding opportunities are often limited for technical staff, so this placement scheme is an invaluable resource that should be taken by any technician seeking to learn or develop a specialist skill!”

Kersti Karu

University College London to the University of Swansea

“I observed the innovative methods for spatial localisation of sterols in brain tissues at the mass spectrometry labs led by Professor William J. Griffiths and Dr. Yuqin Wang.

Integrating this technology into our workflow promises to significantly enhance our research capabilities in UCL Chemistry mass spectrometry facility.

Thank you for providing me with this opportunity. The programme has been immensely beneficial in keeping my professional knowledge up-to-date.”

New national technical networks

ENVIRONMENTAL
SUSTAINABILITY
NETWORK

STRATEGIC
TECHNICAL
LEADERS
NETWORK

TECHNOLOGY
SPECIALISTS
NETWORK

EQUALITY
DIVERSITY
INCLUSION
NETWORK

The UK Higher Education Technicians Summit

The largest event dedicated to UK technical professional development

[Home](#) » Higher Education Technicians Summit

The UK Higher Education Technicians Summit (HETS) is one of the largest conferences for technical professionals in higher education and research.

HETS is dedicated to the professional development of the technician community and celebrates the achievements of technicians through the Papin Prizes.

The one-day event offers a range of workshops, speakers and networking opportunities for the technical community in UK and Ireland.

UK Higher Education Technicians Summit

Quick Links

- [2025 HETS Programme](#)
- [Papin Prize categories](#)
- [Subscribe for updates](#)

HETS 2025

The 2025 event will take place on Wednesday 9 July 2025 in Leicestershire at the Leonardo Conference Centre, Hinckley, LE10 3JA.

It is delivered by the UK Institute for Technical Skills and Strategy. Thanks to a grant from [UK Research and Innovation \(UKRI\)](#) and [Midlands Innovation](#), the higher education and research technical community can attend at no charge.

HETS supports the professional development of technical professionals in higher education and research, by sharing best practice, sector insights and opportunities.

Papin Prizes

The Papin Prizes are dedicated to celebrating the very best technical staff and teams in academia and research.

The national awards recognise and honour the work of technicians in higher education and research; applications are encouraged from individuals who work with technical professionals.

There are ten categories for the 2025 Papin Prizes.

[LEARN MORE](#)

UK Research and Innovation

Papin Prizes

Celebrating technical excellence in higher education and research

[Home](#) » Papin Prizes

The Papin Prizes are the only awards dedicated to celebrating the very best technical staff and teams in academia and research.

These national awards recognise and honour the work of technicians in higher education and research.

In the last decade, these awards have continued to raise the visibility and recognition of technical professionals.

Applications are encouraged from individuals who work with technical professionals including students, staff, collaborators and alumni.

NOMINATIONS NOW CLOSED

Advancing Technical Careers and Building Communities

**257 grants funded
transformative
learning and
development
opportunities**

Advancing Technical Careers and Building Communities

UK Higher Education
Technicians Summit
(HETS) events attended
by over 1250 delegates

Education & Pathways Lab

Transforming technical career pathways, from entry to advanced levels by enabling T-Level industry placements, supporting technical apprenticeships, and reimagining progression routes and opportunities.

Technical Careers Pathways Lab

We are supporting the development of career frameworks for technical staff with higher education and research institutions. Our lab is funded by Research England, part of UK Research and Innovation and builds on the work of the TALENT Commission.

[Home](#) » [Support for Organisations](#) » [Technical Careers Pathway Lab](#)

The UK's technical workforce needs clearer progression, with greater opportunities and mechanisms to move between career pathways and across sectors.

With multiple entry routes into technical careers that are well understood by everyone, we can help build technical capacity and capability in science, technologies, engineering, medicine and the creative industries.

We have set up a Technician Career Pathways Resource on Teams

This is a space to share documents, insights, ideas and conversation about technical pathways.

**APPLY TO JOIN THE
GROUP**

Our Technical Career Pathway Lab priorities

Explore and understand

We are consulting with UK higher education and research institutes to understand existing career pathways for technical professionals and identify areas of excellent practice. We will create a Technical Pathways Lab working group consisting of senior technical leaders, senior technicians and HR professionals who are interested in exploring the career pathways discipline with us.

Inform

We will create valuable communities where best practice, insights and ideas can be shared. We shall create and deliver opportunities to communicate and discuss good practice within the sector. A national symposium is taking place to share ideas and initiatives UK wide. There will be an opportunity to join focussed events and masterclasses to support learning.

Implement

We shall co-design and help to implement effective initiatives that improve career pathways and enhance entry routes into careers. The Technical Career Pathways Lab will select best practice and gather intelligence from the sector to design innovative interventions.

“We are leading nationally on this agenda to help standardise and improve career progression and entry routes into technical careers.

Our national Technical Careers Pathways Lab is building on the recommendations in the TALENT Commission.”

Sarah Allen

Figure 11: Possible entry routes into technical careers within UK HE and research.
 Source: interviews with technical managers and career specialists from a range of UK institutions and discipline areas.

T Level Industry Placements

Become a T Level industry placement host and kick-start the next generation of technical careers

[Home](#) » [Support for Organisations](#) » T Level Industry Placements

We're helping more universities and research institutes across the UK to host technical T Level industry placements in health and science, engineering and manufacturing and digital.

Hosting T Level science placements within technical teams boosts technical skills, increasing capacity and capability in the higher education and research sector.

GET YOUR FREE T LEVEL TOOLKIT

Quick Links

- [T Level Industry Placement hosts](#)
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- [Email us](#)

Case study: The University of Liverpool

Benefits for the technical professionals

Benefits for the university

Jo Hartley-Metcalf

Universities T Levels Support Manager

ITSS Consulting

Offering strategic guidance and tailored support to organisations seeking to optimise their technical workforce

ITSS International

Showcasing the UK's leadership in technical skills, careers, and workforce development by sharing knowledge globally, attracting top technical talent, and creating opportunities for UK technicians to engage with world-class facilities and cutting-edge technologies.

International sharing of best practice

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Ollscoil Teicneolaíochta na Mumhan
Munster Technological University

MALAGHAN
INSTITUTE
OF MEDICAL RESEARCH

International sharing of best practice – Australian Signatories

THE UNIVERSITY OF
SYDNEY

MONASH
University

MU **Murdoch**
University

QCIF
Digital Research³

Press Ctrl+Alt+Delete to unlock.

3:58

Wednesday, November 26

MU Murdoch University

Ngala kwop b... Building a... ure, together.

Press Ctrl+Alt+Delete to unlock.

3:58

Wednesday, November 26

MU Murdoch University

Ngala kwop b... Building a... ure, together.

Partnerships

Australian Government

Department of Education

How Does Diversity Impact Innovation in Team Science?

Scientific Workforce Diversity Seminar Series (SWDSS),
convened by the Chief Officer for Scientific Workforce
Diversity (COSWD) office, NIH

National Institutes of Health
Turning Discovery Into Health

Seminar Series Spotlight

Kelly Vere, MBE

Director of Technical Strategy
University of Nottingham

National Institutes of Health
*Office of the Director
Chief Officer for Scientific Workforce Diversity*

Illustration by Sandbox Studio, Chicago with Corinne Mucha

Visit

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